

AN IMPROVED SMEARED THEORY FOR BUCKLING ANALYSIS OF GRID-STIFFENED COMPOSITE PANELS

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ABSTRACT

Skin-stiffener interactions effects are introduced in a smeared stiffener theory for grid-stiffened panel. The neutral surface profile of the skin-stiffener combination is developed analytically, and the skin-stiffener interaction is accounted for by computing the stiffness due to the stiffener and the skin in the stiffener region about the neutral axis at the stiffener. Buckling loads for stiffened panels are obtained using the smeared stiffness combined with a Rayleigh-Ritz method and are compared with results from detailed finite element analyses.

INTRODUCTION

In aircraft structures, structural efficiency dictates that most primary structures be of stiffened construction. The advent of high-performance composite materials combined with low-cost automated manufacturing using filament-winding and tow-placement techniques has made the grid-stiffened structural concepts a promising alternative to the more traditional stiffened structural concepts. The attractive features of grid-stiffened structures are reported in Ref. [1].

An aircraft in flight is subjected to air loads which are imposed by maneuver and gust conditions. These forces on a structural panel are shown in Figure 1. These internal loads, which depend on the location of the panel in the aircraft structure, may result in either overall panel buckling, buckling of the skin between stiffeners, or stiffener crippling. Hence, an efficient and accurate buckling analysis method for general grid-stiffened panels subjected to combined in-plane loading is needed in order to design grid-stiffened structural panels for different locations in fuselage and wing structures.

A review of the work on stiffened panels and the modeling approaches used is presented in Ref. [2]. One such approach is the smeared stiffener approach [3-5] where the

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stiffened panel is converted mathematically to an unstiffened uniform-thickness panel with equivalent orthotropic stiffnesses. These equivalent or smeared stiffnesses can be used in a Rayleigh-Ritz method to solve for buckling loads of the stiffened panel. The smeared approach is computationally efficient to execute and it can easily account for stiffeners in any direction. However, the smeared approach is applicable to stiffened panels with local buckling loads greater than the global buckling load. These types of panels are also buckling resistant.

In Refs. [4] and [5], a first-order shear-deformation theory (FSDT) has been used for developing an analysis tool based on the smeared stiffener approach. As observed in Refs. [3] and [5], the smeared stiffener approach may overestimate the buckling load of stiffened panels in a certain range of geometric parameters because the smeared stiffener approach does not account for local skin-stiffener interactions. These interactions are included in the present improved smeared stiffener approach making it a more reliable tool in the analysis and design of grid-stiffened panels.

ANALYTICAL APPROACH

The approximate stiffness added by the stiffener to the skin stiffness can be determined by locating the position of the neutral surface in a skin-stiffener combination. The location of the neutral surface is determined theoretically through a study of the local stress distribution near the skin-stiffener interface similar to the approach presented in Ref. [6] for a panel with a blade stiffener. However, the study presented in Ref. [6] is restricted to certain class of orthotropic materials only. The methodology of Ref. [6] has been extended to include all classes of symmetric laminates in Ref. [2] which provides the detailed analytical formulation. The approach presented in Ref. [2] is summarized below.

A grid-stiffened panel may be considered to be an assembly of repetitive units or unit cells (see Figure 2). Any stiffener segment in the unit cell may be isolated in a semi-infinite plate-stiffener model as shown in Figure 2 for a diagonal stiffener. An approach for obtaining the stress distribution in the semi-infinite stiffened plate model is outlined next.

The average membrane stresses in the local coordinate system of the semi-infinite stiffened plate model are obtained by combining the constitutive relations and the strain compatibility equations using a stress function approach. As a result, a fourth-order partial differential equation is obtained.

$$\frac{\partial^4 F}{\partial x^4} - 2e_0 \frac{A_{26}^*}{A_{11}^*} \frac{\partial^4 F}{\partial x^3 \partial \eta} + e_0^2 \frac{(2A_{12}^* + A_{66}^*)}{A_{11}^*} \frac{\partial^4 F}{\partial x^2 \partial \eta^2} - 2e_0^3 \frac{A_{16}^*}{A_{11}^*} \frac{\partial^4 F}{\partial x \partial \eta^3} + \frac{\partial^4 F}{\partial \eta^4} = 0 \quad (1)$$

where A_{ij}^* is given by $[A_{ij}/t]^{-1}$ and A_{ij} is the extensional stiffness of the skin, t is the thickness of the skin, $e_0 = [A_{11}^*/A_{22}^*]^{1/4}$ and $\eta = e_0 y$. This equation is solved by assuming that the stresses decay rapidly as the distance, y , away from the centerline becomes large, the stresses are localized near the stiffener and that a symmetric loading condition exists along the stiffener. The stress function is assumed to be of the form

$$F(x, y) = \text{Re}\{Exp[imk(x + ire_0y)]\} = \text{Re}\{Exp[imk(x + i\eta)]\} \quad (2)$$

where $k = \frac{\pi}{L}$, $m = 1, 2, 3, \dots$ and r is an unknown, x and y are local coordinates. Substituting this stress function into the fourth-order differential equations result in a quartic

equation in r . The membrane solution corresponds to the root with the largest magnitude of the real part for r . That is,

$$F = A_m \text{Exp}[-mke_0 r_R(y - t_s/2)] \cos[mkx] \cos[mke_0 r_I(y - t_s/2)] \quad (3)$$

where r_R and r_I are the real and imaginary parts of the root, respectively, t_s is the thickness of the stiffener, and A_m are coefficients to be determined.

A similar approach is taken for the bending solution using the fourth-order partial differential equation for the out-of-plane deflection in terms of the local coordinate system

$$\frac{\partial^4 w}{\partial x^4} + 4e_b \frac{D_{16}}{D_{11}} \frac{\partial^4 F}{\partial x^3 \partial \eta} + 2e_b^2 \frac{(2D_{12} + D_{66})}{D_{11}} \frac{\partial^4 F}{\partial x^2 \partial \eta^2} + 4e_b^3 \frac{D_{26}}{D_{11}} \frac{\partial^4 F}{\partial x \partial \eta^3} + \frac{\partial^4 F}{\partial \eta^4} = 0 \quad (4)$$

where D_{ij} are the bending stiffnesses of the skin, $e_b = [D_{11}/D_{22}]^{1/4}$ and $\eta = e_b y$. The solution for the out-of-plane deflection is obtained by assuming that the out-of-plane deflection decays as y becomes large and that the loading is symmetric along the stiffener. The out-of-plane deflection is assumed to be of the form

$$w(x, y) = \text{Re}\{\text{Exp}[imk(x + ir e_b y)]\} \quad (5)$$

which on substitution into Equation (4) gives a quartic equation in r . The out-of-plane solution corresponds to the root with the smallest non-zero magnitude of the real part for r . That is

$$w = \text{Exp}[-mke_b r_{Rb}(y - t_s/2)] \cos[mkx] \times \\ \{B_m \sin[mke_b r_{Ib}(y - t_s/2)] + C_m \cos[mke_b r_{Ib}(y - t_s/2)]\} \quad (6)$$

where r_{Rb} and r_{Ib} are the real and imaginary parts of the root, respectively, and B_m and C_m are coefficients to be determined.

These two solutions are valid near the skin-stiffener interface but not within the stiffener. It is assumed that, since the stiffener is thin, the strain within the stiffener is approximately equal to the strain at the edge of the stiffener (at $y = t_s/2$). Using these solutions, the principle of minimum potential energy and conditions from statics, A_m , B_m and C_m can be obtained easily using only the first term of the series ($m = 1$). Finally, the location of the neutral surface, Z' , is obtained from the axial strain as a function of the distance y from the centerline of the stiffener, and the shift in the neutral surface at the stiffener, Z_n , is obtained by setting $y = t_s/2$ in the expression for Z' .

A typical profile of the neutral surface for a plate and stiffener combination is shown in Figure 3. The distance y^* represents the distance from the centerline of the stiffener up to the point where the neutral surface coincides with the mid-surface of the skin. The average distance of the neutral surface over the distance y^* is Z^* . The correction to the plate smeared stiffnesses due to the skin-stiffener interaction is introduced by computing the stiffness of the stiffener and the skin directly contiguous to it with the following criteria.

1. If $y^* < t/4$, then the reference surface for the stiffener is Z_n .
2. If $y^* > t/4$, then the reference surface for the stiffener is Z^* .

In either of these cases, the reference surface for the skin is taken to be its mid-surface.

NUMERICAL RESULTS

Three stiffened panels with different stiffener configurations and simply-supported boundary conditions are used as examples for the above analytical approach. Panel 1 is an axially stiffened panel, Panel 2 is an orthogrid-stiffened panel, and Panel 3 is an example for a general grid-stiffened panel. Finite element analyses of these three panels were carried out to verify the present analytical approach. The finite element analysis codes STAGS [7] and DIAL [8] have been used for this purpose. In the STAGS model, a nine-node shear-flexible element (i.e., STAGS element 480) is used while an eight-node isoparametric shear-flexible element is used in the DIAL model. These analyses indicate that all panels buckle globally under the applied in-plane loadings considered.

Panel 1.

Panel 1 is an axially stiffened panel and its geometric and material details are shown in Figure 4. The panel is subjected to four load cases as shown in Table 1. The STAGS analysis results are compared with solutions from the smeared stiffener approach without skin-stiffener interaction effects (the traditional approach) and with skin-stiffener interaction effects (the present approach). It can be seen that the value of Z_n for the axial stiffener is not small compared to the height of the stiffener. The result obtained by the traditional approach is in good agreement with the STAGS result for the case of axial compression, and the value of the for the present approach is less than the STAGS result by 7.5 percent. For the other load cases, values of the results obtained by the traditional approach are greater than those of STAGS by 8 to 13 percent, and those of the present approach are in good agreement with the STAGS results.

Panel 2.

Panel 2 is an orthogrid panel and its geometric and material details are shown in Figure 5. The panel is subjected to four load cases as shown in Table 2. The DIAL analysis results are compared in Table 2 with solutions from the smeared stiffener approach without skin-stiffener interaction effects and with skin-stiffener interaction effects. It can be seen that the value of Z_n for the transverse stiffener is not small compared to the height of the stiffener. The results obtained using the traditional approach overestimate the DIAL analysis result by 12.6 percent for the axial compression load case, by 4 percent for the transverse compression load case, and by 8.4 percent for the other load cases. The results from the present approach are closer to the DIAL analysis results except for the transverse compression load case which is 5.2 percent less than the DIAL result.

Panel 3.

Panel 3 is a grid stiffened panel and its geometric and material details are shown in Figure 6. The panel is subjected to three load cases as shown in Table 3. The DIAL analysis results are compared with results from the smeared stiffener approach without skin-stiffener interaction effects and with skin-stiffener interaction effects in Table 3. For this panel, the values of Z_n are small compared to the height of the stiffener. The values of the solutions obtained from the traditional approach are approximately 11 percent greater than the DIAL analysis results, and the values of the solutions obtained using the present approach are approximately 6 percent less the DIAL analysis results. For

this case, the solutions obtained using the present approach are conservative since the contribution of A_{16} and D_{16} in the expression for σ_x are not small in the computation of the neutral surface profile for the diagonal stiffener.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

Skin-stiffener interactions effects are introduced in a smeared stiffener theory for grid stiffened panel with blade stiffeners. The skin-interaction effects are introduced by computing the stiffness of the stiffener and the skin in the skin-stiffener region about the neutral axis at the stiffener which is obtained analytically through a study of the local stress distribution near the skin-stiffener interface.

The numerical examples considered show that skin-stiffener interaction effects should be included in the smeared stiffener theory. It provides good correlation of buckling loads with results obtained from detailed finite element analysis. However in a few cases, it does underestimate the buckling load by 5 to 7 percent which may be due to a limitation of the analysis. However, in the preliminary design stage, a smeared stiffener theory with skin-stiffener interaction effects provide buckling loads that are more accurate than the traditional approach.

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Table 1: Results for axially stiffened panel (Panel 1).

X-stiffener: $Z_n = -11.140$ mm., $Z^* = -2.590$ mm., $y^* = 120.679$ mm

		Critical Eigenvalue		
N_x N/mm.	N_{xy} N/mm.	STAGS	Traditional Approach	Present Approach
175.344	0	9.9636	9.9659	9.2135
0	175.344	6.3016	6.7985	6.3483
175.344	175.344	4.9512	5.6018	4.9491
87.672	175.344	5.5023	6.2007	5.5838

Table 2: Results for orthogrid panel (Panel 2).

X-stiffener: $Z_n = -2.410$ mm., $Z^* = -0.418$ mm., $y^* = 0.712$ mm

Y-stiffener: $Z_n = -3.289$ mm., $Z^* = -0.4501$ mm., $y^* = 0.334$ mm

			Critical Eigenvalue		
N_x N/mm	N_y N/mm.	N_{xy} N/mm.	DIAL	Traditional Approach	Present Approach
70.137	0	0	0.7909	0.8903	0.8161
0	35.069	0	0.6281	0.6536	0.5956
70.137	35.069	0	0.3504	0.3799	0.3463
70.137	35.069	8.767	0.3500	0.3796	0.3458

Table 3: Results for grid-stiffened panel (Panel 3).

Y-stiffener: $Z_n = -0.342$ mm., $Z^* = -0.110$ mm., $y^* = 60.035$ mm

D-stiffener: $Z_n = -1.772$ mm., $Z^* = -0.886$ mm., $y^* = 0.606$ mm

			Critical Eigenvalue		
N_x N/mm.	N_y N/mm.	N_{xy} N/mm.	DIAL	Traditional Approach	Present Approach
0	70.137	0	0.3290	0.3646	0.3046
0	70.137	52.603	0.3224	0.3595	0.3008
17.534	70.137	52.603	0.3121	0.3486	0.2917

Figure 1. Aircraft structural applications showing internal forces.

Figure 2. Semi-infinite plate model for a skin-stiffener element.

Figure 3. Typical profile of neutral surface for a skin-stiffener element.

$E_{11} = 131.16E03 \text{ MPa}$
 $E_{22} = 13.04E03 \text{ MPa}$
 $G_{12} = 6.42E03 \text{ MPa}$
 Major Poisson's ratio = 0.38

skin stacking sequence: $[45/-45/-45/45/0/90]_S$
 skin thickness:
 $[4 \times (0.1618 \text{ mm.}) / 0.6325 \text{ mm.} / 1.0566 \text{ mm.}]_S$
 stiffener stacking sequence: $[45/-45/-45/45/0]_S$
 stiffener thickness:
 $[4 \times (0.2090 \text{ mm.}) / 1.714 \text{ mm.}]_S$
 stiffener height = 47.4873 mm

Figure 4 . Axially stiffened panel

$E_{11} = 169.13E03 \text{ MPa}$
 $E_{22} = 11.32E03 \text{ MPa}$
 $G_{12} = 6.0E03 \text{ MPa}$
 Major Poisson's ratio = 0.30

skin stacking sequence: $[45/-45/90/0]_S$
 skin thickness: $[8 \times (0.2032 \text{ mm.})]$
 stiffener stacking sequence: $[0]$
 stiffener thickness: 3.048 mm.
 stiffener height = 12.7 mm

Figure 5. Orthogrid-stiffened panel.

$E_{11} = 169.13E03 \text{ MPa}$
 $E_{22} = 11.32E03 \text{ MPa}$
 $G_{12} = 6.0E03 \text{ MPa}$
 Major Poisson's ratio = 0.30

skin stacking sequence: $[45/-45/90/0]_S$
 skin thickness: $[8 \times (0.2032 \text{ mm.})]$
 stiffener : $[0]$ (stacking sequence)
 stiffener thickness: 2.8575 mm.
 stiffener height = 7.0104 mm

Figure 6. Grid-stiffened panel.